

Research paper

Modeling biodiesel properties by preference learning: Case study of cetane number

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ABSTRACT

The properties and performance of biodiesels depend on the composition of the fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) present. Obtaining new biodiesels is neither a cheap nor a simple task. Therefore, it is important to model their properties in advance in order to know what composition would be needed to fulfill a given requirement. This paper presents a multitask approach that models the behavior of biodiesels using preference learning and also obtains representations of those biodiesels in a feature space by means of an autoencoder. The performance of the system in different configurations is also analyzed, showing its robustness. A case study was conducted to analyze the cetane number, which is an important property in biodiesel. Correlations between the cetane number and the distribution of FAMES have been identified. These correlations are more clearly observed when the FAMES are grouped according to common characteristics, such as the percentage of saturated fatty acids (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) in the biodiesel, or the average number of double bonds (DB). Based on these groupings, it can be observed that the cetane number decreases with increasing unsaturation. Additionally, it was determined that the cetane number value has a minimal or no correlation with the average molecular weight (Mw) of the biodiesel.

1. Introduction

Generating clean energy is a task that is becoming a priority for our society. Since 2015, the United Nations (UN) has been promoting an affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy transition for all, and the decarbonization of fuels plays a crucial role in this process (United Nations, 2023).

According to Malaquias et al. (2019), in 2019, approximately 99.8% of transportation was powered by internal combustion engines (ICEs), and despite government policies, it is expected that by 2050 half of the vehicle fleet will still be powered by ICEs (Senecal and Leach, 2019). Therefore, one of the best options to reduce greenhouse gas emissions is to find alternatives to fossil fuels that can be used in today's vehicle fleet, and one of those alternatives is biodiesel (Santos et al., 2021). Biodiesel is a biofuel derived from vegetable oils or animal fats. It is of particular interest when it is derived from non-edible plant sources that do not require extensive land area for cultivation (Dutta et al., 2014).

Microalgae, photosynthetic microorganisms that can grow in freshwater, seawater or wastewater, do not require arable land, making them an ideal candidate for biodiesel production (Alami et al., 2021).

However, the production of quality biodiesel from microalgae is, to date, an open field of research that presents some difficulties. These include the diversity among the different species of microalgae, the lack of optimized cultivation techniques for subsequent production, and the associated cost of biodiesel production and characterization (Mallick et al., 2016). The conversion of bio-oil extracted from microalgae into biodiesel necessitates the modification of the chemical structure of the triglycerides present in the bio-oil through a series of processes. Among these, the transesterification reaction is the most widely employed. This reaction yields fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), the types and concentration of which determine the properties of the biodiesel obtained. One of the properties is the *cetane number*, which serves as an indicator of the time it will take for the biodiesel to ignite inside the engine piston (Ickes et al., 2009). This is a crucial factor in determining the efficiency of the biofuel.

As outlined by Lü et al. (2011), microalgae could be cultivated and fed with the necessary nutrients so that, when the microalgae oil is transformed, the obtained FAMES provide the desired properties in the biodiesel. Machine learning techniques could be employed to create

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models that, based on the FAME distribution, are capable of predicting the properties of biodiesel. This would be useful to know the FAME distributions that are suitable for a given property and, in this way, be able to guide the cultivation and feeding of microalgae.

Since the properties to be learned are represented by continuous values, this problem has always been solved using regression algorithms. However, developing a predictive model is not a simple task mainly for two reasons. The first is that the number of biodiesel types whose FAME distribution is known is relatively limited (Díez-Valbuena et al., 2024), suggesting that the entire spectrum of existing biodiesel is probably not represented. And the second is that the limited availability of data precludes us from having a representative sample of existing biodiesels, thus raising concerns about the generalization capacity of the generated models.

The objective of this study is to investigate the influence of different FAMES on the cetane number of a biodiesel. The research will employ a regression approach to address the issues previously discussed. An alternative solution will then be proposed: the development of a model that learns to order biodiesel (preference learning) according to a given property, in this case the cetane number. The solution thus obtained can be used to guide the development of new biodiesel. Moreover, by formulating preference learning as a multitask problem involving also an autoencoder, it will be possible to obtain a representation of the biodiesels in a latent space in which they will be organized on the basis of the cetane number and their FAMES composition. This representation can then be used in other learning tasks or for visualizing the data.

As first and main contribution, this work presents a multitask novel approach to working with this type of data sets, based on preference learning and the projection of biodiesels in a latent space. The system presented will allow for:

- The creation of more robust models. The use of biodiesel in pairwise comparisons increases the number of examples available to train the model, which will allow to obtain models with a better generalization capacity. In addition, the multitask approach allows the trained model to learn parameters to be used in both the autoencoder and the preference learning algorithm, which acts as a regularization to both tasks and, therefore, the generated model is more robust against overfitting.
- The obtaining of a ranking of biodiesel. The system will learn to rank the biodiesel according to the target property, being consistent with the preference pairs presented to it during model training.
- Projection of the biodiesels in a reduced dimension space. The system will learn an encoding of the biodiesels in a latent space that can be used mainly (i) for visualization tasks and (ii) for subsequent machine learning processes such as clustering.

The second contribution of this article is the presentation of the results of the case study analyzed, where the FAMES that have more influence on the cetane number are shown. The relationships found between cetane number and the molecular weight (Mw) or the degree of unsaturation suggest a different behavior than previously reported in related work.

The third contribution of this article is the biodiesel database used, which will be made publicly available. To the best of our knowledge, this database is the one that contains the largest number of biodiesel both in quantity and diversity.

The following section will present related work on prediction from FAMES and will discuss the machine learning techniques employed. Then, the proposed multitask method for preference learning and sample visualization will be described. This will be followed by a section devoted to demonstrating the performance obtained by the regression algorithms and by the proposed preference learning algorithm. The final part of the experimental results section will show biodiesel representations obtained from the latent variables, as well as an analysis of different biodiesel properties. Finally, the conclusions of this work will be presented in detail.

Table 1

Number of samples, attributes, and experimental methodology employed by various authors.

Article	# samples	# attributes	Experiment
Mostafaei (2018)	58	3	Hold-out
Alviso et al. (2020-03)	48	2–5	N. S. ^a
Thangaraja et al. (2023)	20	6	N. S. ^b
Huang et al. (2022)	52 ^a	14	Hold-out
Yang et al. (2002)	69	13	Hold-out
Sánchez-Borroto et al. (2014)	68 ^b	10	Hold-out
Rocabruno-Valdés et al. (2015)	128 ^c	16	Hold-out
Ramadhas et al. (2006)	10 ^d	5	Hold-out
Piloto-Rodríguez et al. (2013)	63 ^e	10	Hold-out
Nadai et al. (2013)	44 ^f	7	Hold-out
Bemani et al. (2020)	232 ^g	3	Hold-out
Rahaju et al. (2023)	63 ^e	10	Hold-out
Giwa et al. (2024)	42	5	Hold-out
Bukkarapu and Krishnasamy (2024)	100	13	Hold-out

^a 14 are pure FAMES and 38 are mixtures of different biodiesel or biodiesels with pure FAMES.

^b 10 are pure FAMES.

^c Some biodiesels in this article (could be up to 102) were obtained from Ref. Mohibbeazam et al. (2005) and Winayanuwattikun et al. (2008), where it is indicated that the cetane number was not measured but calculated by a linear function specified in those references.

^d 5 are pure FAMES.

^e 10 are pure FAMES.

^f 15 are pure FAMES.

^g 45 are pure FAMES.

^h The experimental methodology is not specified.

2. Related work

This work employs a combination of machine learning techniques, including preference learning, autoencoders, and multitask learning, to analyze the data from biodiesel samples. This section is dedicated to review and comment on relevant work on the aforementioned techniques and the utilization of machine learning in the context of biodiesel.

2.1. Machine learning applied to biodiesel samples

In recent years, the use of artificial intelligence techniques for biodiesel research has increased. In Table 1, a compilation of works that investigate in the analysis of biodiesels by using machine learning techniques is shown. It indicates the number of examples and attributes used to train the model, as well as the procedure performed for the experimentation. The objective in all these works is to predict the exact value of the property they are analyzing, that is, all of them approach the problem as a regression task.

As it can be seen in the table, most of the works perform a hold-out type experiment, using a portion of examples for the training stage and reserving the rest to evaluate the obtained model. This type of experimentation is effective when there is a high number of examples, however, when there is a reduced number of examples, as it is the case in the works in Table 1, the estimation of the model performance using a hold-out experiment may not be very reliable and in most cases the results would be different if a different partition of the data is used (when working with few examples an experimentation using cross-validation leads to more reliable results). Moreover, in some cases, the results presented are derived from experiments where it is uncertain that the samples have been segregated for the test set (Alviso et al., 2020-03; Thangaraja et al., 2023).

Regarding the technique used to create the models, most of the works in Table 1 present systems based on artificial neural networks (ANN) (Mostafaei, 2018; Thangaraja et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2002; Sánchez-Borroto et al., 2014; Rocabruno-Valdés et al., 2015; Ramadhas et al., 2006; Piloto-Rodríguez et al., 2013; Nadai et al., 2013; Rahaju et al., 2023; Giwa et al., 2024; Bukkarapu and Krishnasamy, 2024),

demonstrating the great acceptance of these type of networks, even though ANNs are known for their tendency to overfit, especially when the number of examples is small. Other works in the table develop their predictive models using evolutionary algorithms (Mostafaei, 2018; Alviso et al., 2020-03; Bemani et al., 2020).

When analyzing the type of biodiesel samples used in the experiments, some authors such as Huang et al. (2022), Sánchez-Borroto et al. (2014), Ramadhas et al. (2006), Piloto-Rodríguez et al. (2013), Nadai et al. (2013), Bemani et al. (2020) and Rahaju et al. (2023) included pure FAMES in their data set, rather than just biodiesels. However, this inclusion can lead to misleading results because the influence of potential interactions among FAMES present in biodiesels on the analyzed property are not fully considered in the models generated. On the other hand, the cetane number of certain biodiesels in the data set utilized by Rocabrundo-Valdés et al. (2015) was calculated from other variables using a linear function rather than being measured in a standard manner.

Another prevalent trend that can be observed in these works is the use of a limited number of attributes (FAMES or calculated values derived from FAMES), which may influence the conclusions drawn.

2.2. Preference learning

Preference learning (Fürnkranz and Hüllermeier, 2011) is a machine learning technique that focuses on learning from pairwise comparisons or preferences between instances, that is, comparisons in which $\mathbf{u} > \mathbf{v}$ represents that \mathbf{u} is preferred than \mathbf{v} . Pairwise preference learning involves learning a model that can predict the preference between two instances rather than predicting their absolute values. The objective is to learn a ranking function, which is commonly referred to as a *utility function*, that can correctly order instances based on their pairwise preferences.

The most straightforward approach to addressing preference learning problems is to transform them into classification problems. Bahamonde et al. (2004) transform each comparison into two examples by calculating the difference between the elements involved in the comparison: one example is assigned a positive class ($\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}, +1$) while the other is assigned a negative class ($\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}, -1$). Once the problem has been transformed, they employ a support vector machine as a classifier, although any other classification algorithm could have been utilized.

Over the years, numerous approaches have been proposed to deal with preference learning tasks. Crammer and Singer (2001) treat preference problems as ordinal regression problems, where the number of ordered classes is equal to the number of examples. They employ a perceptron to predict real-valued scores that give rise to the orderings. However, they can also group the examples into different categories by means of thresholds that their algorithm learns during training. In the solution proposed by Joachims (2002), it is demonstrated that preference learning is an NP-hard problem, which leads him to relax certain constraints in the optimization problem posed for its solution. Among the preference learning algorithms found in the existing literature, the most similar to our system is the one presented by Köppel et al. (2020). Both systems are based on a siamese neural network to obtain the utility function, although our system also incorporates an autoencoder, which allows for the obtaining of projections in a latent space and the creation of a more robust model that is less susceptible to overfitting. Werner (2022) discusses a multitude of preference learning algorithms and provides a complete overview of preference learning if the reader wishes to go deeper.

2.3. Autoencoders

Autoencoders (Ballard, 1987) represent a specific type of neural network architecture that is employed primarily in the context of unsupervised learning. Autoencoders stand out for their ability to find latent variables from the input data without the need for that data to

be labeled (Bank et al., 2023).

The architecture of an autoencoder may vary depending on the specific problem being faced (Berahmand et al., 2024). In general, an autoencoder is composed of two parts (see Fig. 1): the encoder, which compresses the input data to obtain a representation of it in a smaller space (latent space), and the decoder, which reconstructs the original input from its representation in the latent space. The encoding obtained in the latent space is highly useful for other tasks such as visualization or clustering (Berahmand et al., 2024). During training, the objective is to minimize the error in the reconstruction (Bank et al., 2023), that is, the loss between the original input and its reconstructed version. Another notable characteristic of autoencoders is their robustness to noise (Alain and Bengio, 2014).

The most common applications of autoencoders include image denoising (Bajaj et al., 2020), anomaly detection (Chow et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2024), and feature extraction (Zhang et al., 2024).

2.4. Multitask learning

Multitask learning (Caruana, 1997) is an approach in machine learning that seeks to enhance the performance of a model by training it on multiple related tasks simultaneously. In contrast to single-task learning, who has been and is widely used, multitask learning leverages shared information across tasks to improve the model's generalization and predictive ability. This approach is based on the assumption that related tasks share underlying information and common patterns, which can facilitate the learning of more robust and general representations (Zhang and Yang, 2021). The objective of training a model on multiple tasks is to ensure that the knowledge acquired in one task can benefit performance in other related tasks, even if they have different data distributions or specific characteristics.

The effectiveness of multitask learning largely depends on the appropriate selection of tasks and the model architecture used. In practice, multitask models can be designed using techniques such as layer sharing (Zhang and Yang, 2021), where some layers are shared between tasks, and/or by implementing weighted loss functions that assign different degrees of importance to each task during the training stage (Sener and Koltun, 2018).

To the best of our knowledge, the system presented in this paper is the first multitask algorithm that combines preference learning with an autoencoder in order to obtain more robust models and latent space representations of the examples. The main motivation has been to obtain models that are resistant to overfitting when the number of examples is not very large. The fact that both tasks share part of the parameters learned by the model, causes a regularization of the parameters that makes them resistant to overfitting.

3. Proposed method based on preference learning

When the learning objective is not to match as closely as possible the value associated with each sample (in this case the cetane number of a biodiesel), but to generate a ranking in which the biodiesels are correctly ordered by the desired property, the possibility of solving the task by means of preference learning arises. To this end, we begin with a set of preference relations D of the following form:

$$D = \{\mathbf{u}_i > \mathbf{v}_i : i = 1 \dots, n\}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} are real number vectors in \mathbb{R}^d representing the values of the attributes (FAME composition) of two biodiesel examples. In the context of a comparison between two biodiesel samples in the i th comparison, \mathbf{u}_i represents the biodiesel with the highest cetane number, while \mathbf{v}_i is the biodiesel with the lowest cetane number in that comparison.

Starting from this set of comparisons, the objective is to find a *utility function*, $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which is used to assign values that will enable the correct ordering of biodiesel according to its cetane number. In

Fig. 1. Typical architecture of an autoencoder. The goal is for the *output* to be the same as the *input*.

other words, we seek to identify a utility function that maximizes the probability that $f(\mathbf{u}) > f(\mathbf{v})$ whenever the cetane number of \mathbf{u} is greater than that of \mathbf{v} .

A simple approximation to this utility function is to assume that a linear function can solve the task and pose a utility function of the form $f_w(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{u}$, where \cdot represents the dot product and \mathbf{w} is the vector of coefficients that needs to be learned. The above inequality can be developed as follows:

$$f_w(\mathbf{u}) > f_w(\mathbf{v}) \Leftrightarrow 0 < f_w(\mathbf{u}) - f_w(\mathbf{v}) = f_w(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{w} \cdot (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}). \quad (2)$$

It can be seen that when \mathbf{u} has a cetane number greater than \mathbf{v} it must be true that $\mathbf{w} \cdot (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) > 0$ and conversely, if the cetane number of vector \mathbf{u} is less than that of vector \mathbf{v} , then $\mathbf{w} \cdot (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) < 0$. This approach allow us to find the utility function by transforming the problem into a classification task by simply calculating the difference between both biodiesels. The positive examples are the differences $\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}$, while the negative examples are the differences $\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}$. This straightforward method for preference learning has two limitations. On the one hand, it only looks for solutions in linear space and, on the other hand, it does not yield a representation of the biodiesels that can be used for subsequent analysis.

This article proposes a method for simultaneously calculating the utility function and the representation of biodiesel in a latent or feature space. This multitask approach allows to obtain more stable models thanks to the implicit regularization that is achieved by the fact that the model learns parameters that are shared in both tasks. This is very beneficial when working with problems where the number of examples is not too large. The regularization that is incorporated into the learning of the model through the multitasking approach prevents overfitting. To this end, the siamese neural network architecture depicted in Fig. 2 is proposed. The neural network is trained with comparisons contained in \mathcal{D} , with the biodiesel with the highest cetane number of a comparison in \mathcal{D} on the left side of the network and the one with the lowest cetane number (\mathbf{v}) on the right side. This representation of the biodiesels is transmitted through various fully connected layers until a representation of the biodiesels is obtained in a feature space of dimension k . From this representation, the network continues along two paths. One of these paths leads through a completely connected layer (without activation function) towards the valuation of biodiesel. The other path leads to the reconstruction of biodiesel through a series of layers that act as a decoder for the autoencoder. As a siamese network, both the right and left parts share the same weights. The hyperbolic tangent has been used as the activation function since it ensures that the parameters are bounded in values between -1 and $+1$, thus avoiding excessively large values that could lead to overfitting or

convergence problems.

A neural network that addresses two tasks is therefore proposed: (i), it attempts to learn an appropriate utility function to perform biodiesel orderings, and (ii) it searches for a representation of the biodiesels in a feature space of dimension k . During the training stage of this neural network, two loss functions will be involved, the weights of which must be appropriately adjusted to obtain the final loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}([\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}], [\hat{\mathbf{u}}, \hat{\mathbf{v}}]) = \rho \cdot \mathcal{L}_p(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) + (1 - \frac{\rho}{2}) \cdot \mathcal{L}_a(\mathbf{u}, \hat{\mathbf{u}}) + (1 - \frac{\rho}{2}) \cdot \mathcal{L}_a(\mathbf{v}, \hat{\mathbf{v}}), \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ represent the reconstruction obtained by the autoencoder of the vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} respectively. \mathcal{L}_a is the loss function that the autoencoder will use and that corresponds to the *mean square error* applied to the vector with the attributes of the biodiesel and the vector that is obtained after the reconstruction provided by the autoencoder. \mathcal{L}_p is the loss function for the preferences, and it is associated with correctly ordering the two biodiesels in the comparison. If the biodiesel \mathbf{u} has a higher cetane number than the biodiesel \mathbf{v} , it is desirable that $f(\mathbf{u}) > f(\mathbf{v})$. In order to increase the probability that the utility function does its job correctly, the strategy of *maximizing the margin* will be employed, guaranteeing that the difference is at least one unit, that is, $f(\mathbf{u}) \geq f(\mathbf{v}) + 1$. This leads to the following loss function for preferences:

$$\mathcal{L}_p(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \max(0, 1 - f(\mathbf{u}) + f(\mathbf{v})). \quad (4)$$

In order to weight the loss functions, the hyperparameter ρ , which varies in the range $[0, 1]$, will be used in Eq. (3). This will give equal weight to the loss committed in the reconstruction of the two biodiesels.

Preference learning is also a useful tool when regression algorithms do not perform as expected, which can happen when the number of examples is not sufficient or the examples do not represent all possible situations. In these cases, preference learning can be of great help since from n examples up to $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ comparisons can be obtained. This enables the set of comparisons to capture more nuances than those present in the original set of examples. Furthermore, when combined with the autoencoder, more useful and robust models can be obtained.

4. Experimental results

This section will evaluate the performance of the proposed system in two distinct facets: obtaining a utility function that aligns with the pairwise comparisons and obtaining biodiesel representations in a latent space.

A description of the data set utilized will be provided, followed by an analysis of the results obtained by approaching the problem as a regression task. Subsequently, certain implementation details of the

Fig. 2. Siamese network architecture implemented to simultaneously obtain the utility function and the representation of biodiesels in the feature space.

preference learning algorithm will be discussed and the performance of both, the learned utility function and the autoencoder, will be shown, analyzing also the influence of the hyperparameter ρ in the learning process. This section will conclude with a graphical representation of the obtained biodiesel representations.

4.1. Data set description

The database was manually created by consulting more than 100 articles published between 2002 and 2022, resulting in a total of 543 biodiesel examples. For the collection of these biodiesel samples, data published in articles found on academic websites such as *Web of Science*, *Google Scholar* or *Scopus* were used. These websites were searched for publications using terms such as *FAME distribution*, *Biodiesel properties*, *Biodiesel characterization* or *Biodiesel composition*. These articles, in turn, led to other articles in which new data were published, which were also incorporated into the database. In this way, the largest quantity and variety of biodiesels available in the literature were incorporated. It is worth noting that 57.7% of the samples correspond to first-generation biodiesel, 37.1% to second-generation biodiesel, and 5.2% to third-generation biodiesel, which is consistent with the historical development of biodiesel (Singh et al., 2024).

For each biodiesel found in a publication, up to 34 different types of FAME and all the properties that the authors published (including the cetane number) were noted. To the best of our knowledge, no biodiesel database of similar size and scope existed. In addition to the distribution of FAMES of each biodiesel, other characteristics were also noted, such as the average number of double bonds (DB), the percentage of saturated, monounsaturated or polyunsaturated fatty acids (SFA/MUFA/PUFA), and the average molecular weight (Mw) of biodiesels.

As the objective of this article is to investigate the influence of the different FAMES on the cetane number, consequently those biodiesels for which the total sum of FAMES does not reach 90% were excluded from the experimentation. Finally, the experimentation was performed on 466 biodiesel described by 34 FAMES. Fig. 3 depicts the frequency of occurrence of each FAME in the 466 biodiesel samples utilized in the experiment. As illustrated, only 13 FAMES exhibited a notable presence.

Table 2

Results obtained as a regression task.

System	MAE	MSE	R^2
Mean predictor	5.36	57.22	0.0074
Decision Tree	3.82	42.47	0.2522
Random Forest	3.44	33.27	0.4143
XGBoost	3.57	36.67	0.3543
SVR (linear kernel)	3.54	32.50	0.4278
SVR (polynomial kernel)	3.46	33.16	0.4161
SVR (RBF kernel)	3.61	37.16	0.3457
Neural Network (1 hidden layer)	4.16	39.73	0.3005
K-Nearest Neighbors	3.85	37.75	0.3353
Bayesian Ridge	3.55	32.21	0.4329
Gradient Boosting	3.54	32.31	0.4311
Alviso et al. (2020-03)	4.16	37.61	0.3430
Piloto-Rodríguez et al. (2013)	3.90	36.27	0.4450

4.2. Solving the problem as a regression task

As a preliminary approach to addressing this issue, regression algorithms were employed to develop a model that could predict the cetane number of a biodiesel from the FAME distribution. For this experiment, well-established regression algorithms were utilized, and a 5-fold cross-validation was conducted. As some of the algorithms utilized hyperparameters that required tuning, a *grid hyperparameter search* was conducted in each iteration of the cross-validation process (the grid search was conducted using only the training examples from each iteration of the cross-validation).

As illustrated in Table 2, predicting the mean value of the cetane number observed in the training set results in a 5.36 *mean absolute error* (MAE). The remaining systems demonstrate an improvement in this result to varying degrees. Random Forest achieves the most favorable performance in terms of MAE, Bayesian Ridge exhibits the lowest *mean square error* (MSE) and the equation presented by Piloto-Rodríguez et al. (2013) obtains the highest *coefficient of determination* (R^2). Two equations published in the works shown in Table 1 (Alviso et al., 2020-03; Piloto-Rodríguez et al., 2013) have also been included in the experimentation and their performances do not differ from those obtained with the rest of the algorithms.

These results appear to be promising in comparison to the average predictor, however, 45% of the biodiesels present in the data set are

Fig. 3. FAME frequency of the 466 examples gathered in the data set.

within a range of ± 3.44 with respect to the average value of the cetane number of the biodiesels present in the data set (54.27). This implies that the models obtained from the regression algorithms analyzed can make critical errors for the proposed application (since 3.44 is the best MAE obtained in the experiments).

We can also observe in Table 2 that the SVR with linear kernel obtains better results than if nonlinear kernels are used. This is because the polynomial and RBF kernels allow the SVR to better adapt to the training examples, producing in this case an overfitting that increases the error obtained by such models.

4.3. Solving the problem as a preference learning task

The performance obtained by the regression methods in the previous section calls into question the usefulness of such models. Although a lot of effort has been devoted to the creation of the biodiesel database, it is possible that the number of samples collected is still not sufficient to obtain a model capable of predicting the cetane number. In view of this, instead of predicting the value, the preference learning algorithm presented in Section 3 will be used, which will allow obtaining a utility function capable of ranking the biodiesels and capable of representing them also in the latent space.

To analyze the performance of the preference learning system presented in this article, a 5-fold cross-validation has been conducted in accordance with the methodology employed for regression algorithms. Although the preference algorithms are trained from the pairwise comparisons contained in the set \mathcal{D} (Eq. (1)), the division of examples into the different folds must be done on biodiesels and the comparisons must be created specifically for each training and test set (after having performed the division by biodiesel), thus ensuring that the data for a biodiesel in the test set does not appear in any comparison of the training set.

To obtain comparisons from a set of biodiesels, one could generate all possible comparisons between the biodiesels in the set by comparing them pairwise. This would result in $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ comparisons if we have n biodiesel. The number of comparisons generated could be excessive and slow down the training of the models, so in this paper we have chosen to generate 50 comparisons for each biodiesel when creating the training sets and to generate all possible pairwise comparisons in

the test set, in order to obtain the most realistic performance estimate possible. We performed the tests with different number of comparisons per biodiesel (between 1 and 50) to generate the training set and observed that from 10 comparisons per biodiesel the performance of the models is quite stable.

An implementation of the architecture proposed in Fig. 2 has been carried out using the TensorFlow library (Abadi et al., 2016) with Adam as optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2014). This implementation will be referred to as SNPLV in Table 4. As a dimension for the feature space k , the values 2, 4, 8, and 16 have been selected to work with. The remaining system hyperparameters were previously fixed using a validation set, and these are the values finally selected for the hyperparameters: learning_rate = 0.001, $\rho = 0.6$, autoencoder layer dimensions = (32 – 16 – 8 – 4 – 8 – 16 – 32). In any case, the system is quite stable at values close to those indicated, as can be seen in Table 5, where values of ρ between 0.5 and 0.9 offer similar results, or in Table 4, where values of k between 4 and 16 give similar results. We have also analyzed the sensitivity of the model to different values of the learning rate during the training stage (see Table 3), and a fairly stable behavior has been observed in values close to 0.001. In all runs, the algorithm was allowed to learn over five epochs.

Given the influence that the initialization of the weights of a neural network can have on the results, five repetitions of the cross-validation were carried out for this system, and the average of the results obtained is shown in Tables 4 and 5.

Another preference learning system has also been implemented by transforming the preference learning problem into a classification task. In this case, the model learns to distinguish positive differences, $\{\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}, +1\}$, from negative differences, $\{\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}, -1\}$. This approach, explained in Section 3, uses Eq. (2). In this case, a support vector machine (SVM_{pref} in Table 4), that has been trained under the same conditions as the system presented in this article, has been used as a classifier.

As illustrated in Table 4, the system SNPLV exhibits a higher percentage of success than SVM_{pref}, with the exception of biodiesel projections into a two-dimensional feature space. This outcome is logical, given the difficulty in identifying a two-dimensional space that adequately captures the nuances of a problem. Nevertheless, it can be observed that from four dimensions, the system has already achieved stable results above 77% of correct comparisons, that is, it gets almost

Table 3
Model performance in a 5-fold cross-validation when varying the learning rate during model training.

	Learning rate									
	0.005	0.004	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.0009	0.0008	0.0007	0.0006	0.0005
% Accuracy	77.18	77.43	77.54	77.82	77.96	78.13	78.28	78.14	77.98	77.37
MSE	24.81	20.61	32.75	37.15	46.68	48.65	50.63	53.37	56.55	60.52

Table 4

Percentage of pairwise comparisons correctly classified and execution time when the problem is treated as a preference learning task.

System	% Accuracy	Time in seconds
SNPLV _{k=2}	62.34	60
SNPLV _{k=4}	77.96	59
SNPLV _{k=8}	77.37	59
SNPLV _{k=16}	77.51	58
SVM _{pref}	76.59	3201

4 out of 5 comparisons right.

In terms of execution time¹, SNPLV is much faster than SVM_{pref}. The number of comparisons in the training set greatly affects SVM_{pref}. If only 10 comparisons per biodiesel were used in the training set, the times would drop to 110 s for SVM_{pref} and 26 s for SNPLV, lowering their accuracies to 76.40% and 77.41% respectively.

4.4. Influence of loss functions

SNPLV simultaneously addresses two tasks: learning the utility function and representing biodiesels in the feature space. Consequently, the weight assigned to each loss function during the model training stage can influence the performance of each task. For this purpose, the hyperparameter ρ , which takes values between 0 and 1, is introduced into Eq. (3). A value of 1 indicates that all the weight of the loss function is allocated to the task of learning the utility function, while a value of 0 indicates that all the weight is allocated to the representation task (autoencoder).

Table 5 illustrates the impact of ρ on the performance of system SNPLV_{k=4}, as demonstrated by conducting the experiment under the identical conditions explained in the previous section. It is observed that by reducing the weight of learning the utility function, the percentage of correctness in the comparisons declines significantly. Conversely, values of ρ exceeding or equaling 0.5 achieve a relatively stable percentage of success above 77%. The MSE obtained by comparing the original biodiesel vectors with those reconstructed by the autoencoder does not exhibit a clear trend. It could be expected that the MSE would decrease as the weight of the autoencoder loss function increases. However, the MSE remains stable at 48.2, with improved results being observed at higher values of ρ . This indicates that at low values of ρ , the autoencoder overfits, resulting in poorer cross-validation results. Therefore, a medium/high value of ρ is necessary for the utility function learning process to act as a regulator in the autoencoder learning process.

4.5. Ablation study

Table 5 presents the extreme values of ρ , which are used to observe the behavior of the system in an ablation study. When $\rho = 0$, the weight of the loss function is entirely focused on minimizing the MSE obtained by reconstructing the biodiesels using the autoencoder. This results in a significant reduction in the percentage of correctly classified comparisons.

¹ These experiments were run on a MacBook Pro with an M2 Pro processor and 16 GB of RAM.

Table 5

Influence of ρ on model performance. $\rho = 1$ indicates that all the weight falls on the preference learning loss function.

ρ	% Accuracy	MSE
0	44.95	48.280
0.1	45.75	48.285
0.2	49.29	48.269
0.3	57.22	48.247
0.4	70.17	48.006
0.5	77.67	47.048
0.6	77.96	46.680
0.7	77.76	46.572
0.8	77.48	46.404
0.9	77.51	46.851
1	77.19	114.018

However, when $\rho = 1$, the system focuses only on correctly classifying the comparisons, with the loss function of the autoencoder being disabled. This approach results in the system achieving a high success rate in the preference learning task, while the autoencoder is unable to fulfill its intended purpose, resulting in an exceedingly high MSE.

It is then observed that both, the learning of the utility function and the learning of the autoencoder, are necessary for the correct training of the model. In fact, for the data set under consideration, the system with $\rho = 0.6$ presents good and balanced results in both metrics.

Analyzing the convenience of using a multitask approach ($\rho = 0.6$) versus solving both tasks separately ($\rho = 0$ or $\rho = 1$), the results show that the multitask approach reduces the MSE, going from 48.28 to 46.68, and that it increases accuracy, going from 77.19% to 77.96%. Using the multitask approach gives stability to the model through the regularization obtained by the fact that the model learns parameters that are shared in both tasks. This is very beneficial when working with problems in which the number of examples is not too large. The regularization that is incorporated into the learning of the model through the multitask approach prevents overfitting.

4.6. Biodiesel visualization

The algorithm presented in this paper, SNPLV, while learning the utility function, also learns a representation of the biodiesels in a feature space where the biodiesels are organized by combining the influence of their original attributes (FAMES) and how these attributes affect their cetane number. These representations can be useful for visualizing data for explanatory purposes or for addressing other learning tasks.

If the feature space learned by the autoencoder were a two- or three-dimensional space, the biodiesels could be plotted in those spaces. However, this is not usually the case. When the feature space is of higher dimension, a common way to represent them graphically is to use the algorithm t-SNE (van der Maaten and Hinton, 2008), which allows higher dimensional vectors to be displayed in 2 or 3 dimensions. Fig. 4(a) shows in 2-D (using to the t-SNE algorithm) the projections obtained by SNPLV for the biodiesels in the feature space. The greater the intensity of the color, the higher the cetane number in the biodiesel. It can be observed that the biodiesels are grouped in an orderly manner, indicating that the obtained representations are consistent with the learned utility function.

This projection of biodiesels in the feature space can be utilized to observe the relationships between the cetane number and other

Fig. 4. Representation of the biodiesels based on the value/content of their following features: (a) Cetane Number, (b) SFA, (c) MUFA, (d) PUFA, (e) Double Bonds, and (f) Molecular weight.

properties (Fig. 4) or attributes of biodiesels (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 illustrates the relationships between the cetane number and certain properties calculated based on the FAME distribution. The greater the intensity of the color, the higher content of SFA/MUFA/PUFA, number of DB or Mw value. As illustrated in the Figure, a correlation can be observed between the cetane number and other attributes, including the percentage of saturated fatty acids (SFA) (Fig. 4(b)), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) (Fig. 4(c)), polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) (Fig. 4(d)) of the biodiesel, and the average amount of double bonds (DB) (Fig. 4(e)). From Fig. 4(b), it can be observed that high percentages of SFA correspond to higher cetane numbers (correlation: 0.507). It appears that as the degree of unsaturation increases, either due to an increase in the DB or the percentage of PUFA in the biodiesel (Figs. 4(e) and 4(d)), the cetane number decreases (corr.: -0.664 respect DB, -0.641 respect PUFA). However, Fig. 4(c) indicates that for high percentages of MUFA, the cetane number seems to be unaffected (corr.: 0.207). In Fig. 4(e), for DB around 1 (equivalent to high

percentages of MUFA), the biodiesels are positioned in average cetane number zones. This suggests that in biodiesels with blends of different FAMES, the amount of DB does not influence the cetane number until it represents a significant percentage or the FAMES are polyunsaturated. Furthermore, a comparison between the cetane number and the average molecular weight (Mw) of the biodiesel (Fig. 4(f)) reveals that there is not a very clear relationship (corr.: 0.264). These results differ from those published by other authors, such as Klopfenstein (1985) and Knothe et al. (2003). This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that their respective studies analyzed the cetane number of the FAMES individually, rather than in a mixture such as any biodiesel. When a biodiesel is composed of several FAMES, the molecular weight does not appear to be a significant factor in determining the cetane number.

Fig. 5 depicts the projections of the biodiesels that contain the most prevalent FAMES, which allows for the establishment of a relationship between the cetane number and these FAMES. The greater the intensity

Fig. 5. Representation of the biodiesels based on the percentage of the FAME: (a) C12:0, (b) C16:0, (c) C18:0, (d) C18:1, (e) C18:2, and (f) C18:3.

of the color, the higher content of the corresponding FAME. This analysis of the FAMES with the highest presence and their relationship to the cetane number reveals that biodiesels with high percentages of C12:0, C16:0 or C18:0 are situated in areas with high cetane numbers (corr.: 0.415 respect C12:0, 0.264 respect C16:0, 0.258 respect C18:0), while biodiesels with high percentages of FAMES such as C18:2 or C18:3 are positioned in areas with low cetane numbers (corr.: -0.489 respect C18:2, -0.406 respect C18:3). This indicates that the degree of unsaturation, particularly of the polyunsaturated compounds, is of greater importance than the chain length. Focusing on the FAME C18:1 graph, it reveals that this FAME is distributed in areas with an average cetane number (corr.: 0.213).

4.7. Discussion

Regression algorithms have shown poor performance when confronted with the task of predicting the cetane number. The obtained

coefficients of determination consistently fall below 0.45, indicating that the generated models are not useful for some applications. This may be due to the fact that there are not enough biodiesel samples available (although the database created is the largest known). This shortage of samples means that not all possible situations are well represented in the training set, potentially leading to overfitting in algorithms that are more readily adapted to training examples. This situation seems to be happening with the SVR, which performs worse when using nonlinear kernels.

As an alternative to regression algorithms, the proposed algorithm combines preference learning with an autoencoder to obtain, on the one hand, a utility function capable of ordering and, on the other hand, representations of the biodiesels in a latent space. This approach relaxes the problem to be solved since, instead of trying to predict the cetane number, the aim is to be able to rank biodiesels on the basis of their cetane number (without predicting its value). The results obtained show a good performance of the model, achieving an accuracy of almost

78%. This good result is mainly due to two factors: (i) when learning from pairwise comparisons, the number of potential training examples is much larger, since from n biodiesel samples up to $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ comparisons can be obtained and (ii) when simultaneously learning the utility function and the autoencoder representation, a regularization of the parameters shared by both tasks is automatically applied. Therefore, both tasks are important, as has been demonstrated in the ablation study carried out.

Once the proposed system has computed the biodiesel representations in the latent space, these representations can be used for different purposes. For example, they could be used as an intermediate step to solve other machine learning tasks such as clustering. Another popular application of the representations obtained by autoencoder is their use for visualization. In this article the t-SNE algorithm has been employed as a tool to facilitate the visualization of the representations in 2 dimensions, but other techniques could have been utilized, such as principal component analysis (PCA) projecting the 2 most explanatory components. The visualization of these representations has shown that high percentages of saturated fatty acids are related to high values of cetane number, while high values of PUFA and DB have been observed to inversely affect this property. Analyzing FAME distribution directly, the visualization of the representations shows that high presence of C18:0 or C18:3 is associated with high values of cetane number, while high values of C18:2 cause the cetane number to decrease. All this has been numerically corroborated by calculating the correlations.

The presented system, being based on a preference learning algorithm, focuses on sorting biodiesel samples based on cetane number. The applications of this solution can be very broad. For example, in the early stages of new biodiesel development, knowing where a new biodiesel will be ranked can be used to discard it before processing if it is not promising, thus reducing costs. It can also be useful to discern which feedstocks lead to a better biodiesel or could be used in quality control processes of the feedstocks themselves.

Although in this paper the experimentation has been focused on the analysis of the cetane number, any other biodiesel property could have been used. However, as discussed above, it makes more sense to use the method presented in this paper when regression algorithms have difficulties in obtaining a model with good performance for the property to be studied. In these cases, using the proposed multitask algorithm will yield a robust model capable of ordering the biodiesels as a function of the property studied and also capable of obtaining representations of the biodiesels in the latent space.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents an alternative approach to biodiesel modeling, which has traditionally been performed using regression algorithms. The algorithm presented is a multitask system capable of simultaneously learning a utility function while learning a representation of the examples in a feature space. For this purpose, a neural network architecture has been designed that includes a siamese network for learning preferences that also contains an autoencoder. This architecture has been tested in the modeling of biodiesel properties, specifically with the cetane number property. However, the same method could be applied to any other property. The trained model achieved an accuracy of nearly 4 out of 5 comparisons right, generating a reliable biodiesel ranking. This analysis has focused on the cetane number property and the generated ranking could be used, for example, to determine if a biodiesel is going to have a suitable ignition delay.

Furthermore, the representations obtained in the feature space are consistent with the learned utility function and can be utilized for subsequent learning tasks or for the generation of graphical representations. With regard to the cetane number, it can be posited from these representations that the cetane number is primarily influenced by the degree of unsaturation of the compounds that comprise the biodiesel. Consequently, the higher the degree of saturation, the higher the cetane

number, although this relationship is less pronounced at low levels of unsaturation. As the value increases, the relationship becomes more pronounced.

Another conclusion that can be drawn from the graphical representations is that the cetane number hardly depends on the molecular weight, despite other studies indicating the contrary. This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that these studies always used isolated FAME and their behavior does not seem to be replicated when the biodiesel is composed of several FAME molecules. When some FAME molecules are mixed with others, it seems that this relationship is lost and that other properties such as the degree of unsaturation govern the behavior.

Different variants of the algorithm have been left unexplored and can be analyzed in future work. One line to pursue may be to use alternative loss functions for the autoencoder or, taking advantage of the multitasking approach of the algorithm, to compute several utility functions simultaneously for several biodiesel properties so that the dependence between different properties could be analyzed.

Finally, it should be noted that the main field of application of the presented algorithm is the extraction of knowledge from data sets where it is difficult to obtain a predictive regression model. In such scenarios, preference learning algorithms can generate useful models, although these models will be limited to obtaining an ordering, rather than predicting the value of the property to be learned (this implies a relaxation of the initial problem that will allow for the generation of more useful models). From the point of view of the cetane number, obtaining a utility function capable of ordering biodiesels will allow its application in situations where it is sufficient to determine whether the cetane number value belongs to a certain range.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Guillermo Díez-Valbuena: Writing – original draft, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Alejandro García-Tuero:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Eduardo Rodríguez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Antolin Hernández Battez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jorge Díez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data is available in the repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11058315> for their use.

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